

Extent of Use and Perceptions of the Pros and Cons of AI-Powered Chatbots in Education: Teachers' and Students' Insights

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in education is changing teachers' and students' experiences in the classroom. Chatbots are some of the most readily available AI tools today. This technology offers immediate support for both academic and administrative work. This study explores the extent of use and perceptions of the pros and cons of AI chatbots among the teachers and students of Eastern Samar State University–Maydolong Campus. Using a mixed-method, specifically, a sequential explanatory approach, quantitative data were collected using structured questionnaires, while qualitative data were collected through interviews and focus group discussions. This method was used to determine the perceptions of students and teachers regarding the integration of AI chatbots in education, and further explained the qualitative data.

Results revealed a reliance on AI chatbots for various academic functions, both by students and teachers. Students commonly use chatbots for

searching information, writing assistance, and study support, while teachers use the chatbots for instructional materials preparation, simplifying lessons, and enhancing lesson engagement. Despite the benefits, respondents pointed out concerns associated with misinformation, academic dishonesty, and a decrease in critical skills. Additionally, teachers expressed concern that AI chatbots might reduce fairness and accuracy in students' assessments. While students' biggest concern is their overreliance on this technology, which could lead to addiction.

Lastly, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed a clear and significant difference between how teachers and students view the pros and cons of AI chatbots.

This study highlights the need to establish boundaries on the use of AI in education through strategies and the integration of the responsible use of AI chatbots into the curriculum.

Keywords: *AI chatbots, Sequential Explanatory, Artificial Intelligence, Perception, Pros and Cons*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The emergence of AI chatbots has sparked a conversation about their effectiveness and controversies in education. AI chatbots date back to the 1960s and have evolved as people demanded automated communication systems. Since the introduction of ChatGPT in 2022, there has been a significant rise in the number of users recorded. This represents a change in the domain's paradigm, attracting more than 100 million users in just the first two months, which has compelled other chatbots to enhance their programs (Dempere et al., 2023).

Chatbot can be defined as an intelligent conversational application that can simulate natural language conversation between machines and humans through text or voice input and output (Callejas & Griol, 2016). AI chatbots can deliver instant assistance by responding to inquiries, providing clarifications, and presenting other pertinent resources for both students and teachers. Built to simulate human dialogue through text or voice, AI-powered chatbots conversationally share information (Labadze et al., 2023). AI chatbots are utilized in different sectors, including education, to address problems like the teacher-to-student ratio, which has led to insufficient attention to personalized learning for students. Thus, this allows the students to engage in self-directed learning through its use. Students view AI chatbots as very beneficial and encouraging when it comes to personal task assistance and obtaining prompt feedback and support with writing, coding, and academic responsibilities. However, despite the opportunities of Chatbots, students have expressed worries regarding the accuracy and reliability of the chatbot answers, along with possible adverse effects on their learning experiences, analytical skills, self-discipline, and creativity (Schei et al. 2024). This kind of AI system risks potential technology exploitation; students may take shortcuts in doing their literary work and written output, such as essay completion, reflection papers, assignments, endangering the growth of essential competencies (Shrivastava, 2022). According to Dempere, et al. (2023), "It is significant to note that this AI chatbot sparks risk in education by deteriorating students' motivation to work on their own". Teachers and professors are uneasy about potential academic fraud using this kind of technology.

Furthermore, as educators recognize the importance of a technologically driven education, teachers have extensively used state-of-the-art technology to enhance their teaching pedagogy. Educators view AI chatbots as effective conversational tools because of their ability to process and generate text based on the data entered. Nonetheless, there are numerous concerns regarding using AI chatbots in education, particularly regarding the accuracy of this technology's information (Nguyen, 2024; Labadze, 2023). There have been ongoing attempts to integrate AI chatbot systems into educational settings; however, the effective adoption of innovative instructional technologies significantly depends on the perspectives of the teachers delivering the lessons. The AI chatbot serves as a valuable support tool to assist students in their learning, providing help that teachers may not always be able to offer (Yang et al. 2022).

In the educational sector, the accessible and easy-to-use interface of ChatGPT and other comparable AI chatbots may lower obstacles to their broad implementation across various educational environments and among diverse groups of educators and students (Kasneci et al., 2023). Educators can utilize this AI chatbot's capabilities to improve their planning (for instance, by recognizing the requirements of their students and getting to know them better), implementation (such as by offering immediate feedback and supporting teacher intervention), and evaluation (by employing automated essay grading) (Celik & Muukkonen, 2022).

There is a rapidly expanding body of knowledge concerning the application of AI chatbots in education. Nevertheless, our grasp of the factors influencing students in higher education to adopt and interact with these technologies, as well as the impact of this engagement on their critical thinking, creativity, problem-solving abilities, and overall learning processes, remains insufficient (Ali et al. 2024). Numerous problems in this AI chatbot system have gained significant attention and need careful

examination to understand its impact on the education field. While the global trend continues towards implementing AI Chatbots into education, the current research concentrates more on their technical capabilities and broad scope of application, little is known about how these tools are used in real settings and how teachers and students respond to their advantages and disadvantages differently. Accordingly, this study investigated the perceptions of Eastern Samar State University, Maydolong, students, and teachers towards the pros and cons of AI chatbots in education, as well as the extent to which this technology is used in educational settings. Most studies focus on either teacher views or student views, with little regard for the difference in how the two groups view and use chatbots. This research would particularly offer an in-depth understanding of how teachers and students of ESSU-Maydolong use AI chatbots in their daily school activities, and what challenges, benefits, and limitations exist from the perspective of both, while including implications of such factors on the educational process. Kasneci et al. (2023) pointed out that a lack of understanding of AI capabilities and limitations might lead to misuse and overreliance on AI technologies by teachers and learners.

While many studies lean heavily on descriptive or correlational approaches, few take the extra step to truly dive deeper. There's a noticeable gap in research that uses a sequential exploratory method to uncover the richer, more nuanced layers of perception regarding the use of AI chatbots in education.

Research Question:

This study's primary goal is to explore both the students' and teachers' perceptions of the pros and cons of AI-powered chatbots in education. Specifically, this research wants to answer the following:

RQ1: What are the perceptions of teachers and students in integrating AI chatbots in the educational context?

These are the following sub-questions of the study:

SQ1: What kind of AI chatbots do the students frequently use?

SQ2: What kind of AI chatbots do the teachers frequently use?

SQ3: What is the extent of the students' use of AI chatbots in doing their academic tasks?

SQ4: What is the extent of the teachers' use of AI chatbots in teaching?

SQ5: What are the pros and cons perceived by the students regarding AI chatbots in doing academic tasks?

SQ6: What are the pros and cons perceived by the teachers in integrating AI chatbots in teaching?

SQ7: Is there a significant difference between the students' and teachers' perceived pros and cons of using AI chatbots in education?

Conceptual Framework

This study was anchored in the prominent theories of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Davis (1986), Value Acceptance Model (VAM), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Technology Use (UTAUT), Venkatesh et al. (2003), and Meta-UTAUT (UTAUT2), Dwevidi et al. (2021). These theories were commonly utilized to comprehensively understand the users' perceptions and attitudes toward the acceptance of technology. The TAM and VAM models emphasize the importance of *perceived ease of use* and *perceived usefulness* as key contributors to the users' intended behavior toward technology acceptance. On the other hand, UTAUT and Meta-UTAUT further discuss the deeper concept of the TAM and VAM, in which these models allow us to examine the direct cause of users' intended behavior towards adopting technology.

Furthermore, user perception of which AI chatbot enhances their productivity and task performance is constituted by the concept of TAM, which is perceived usefulness. Meanwhile, AI chatbot usability is aligned with the concept of *perceived ease of use*. These underlying variables are the factors that this study considered to understand the individual acceptance of this AI Chatbot technology.

Likewise, this study looked into UTAUT, which considered several key factors in technology acceptance: performance expectation (*PE*), the belief that ChatGPT will make their learning tasks easier; *effort expectation (EE)*, users' perception of the effort required to use AI chatbot; *social influence (SI)*, the belief that users use ChatGPT due to the influence of peers and *family*; and *facilitating condition (FC)*, the degree to which users perceive AI chatbot has the availability of necessary information needed (Habibi et al., 2024).

Guided by theories and literature, this framework construct examined the difference between the students' and teachers' perceived benefits and perceived concerns about AI chatbots. Understanding the perception of teachers and students towards AI chatbots can necessitate the potential adaptation of this technology to education settings. The perception of teachers and students towards AI chatbot must need to be understood to tweak it according to implementation in the education setting. Understanding and critically evaluating this concept would allow the policymakers to gather critical information in enabling them to come up with well-informed policy propositions that are geared toward offsetting the potential drawbacks of AI chatbot as well as ensuring its useful implementation within the classroom.

This framework illustrates the interplay of naturally occurring variables, specifically the extent of use of AI chatbots by students and teachers, as well as their perceptions of the advantages and disadvantages of these tools within an educational context. It seeks to examine the potential significant differences in respondents' perceptions regarding the utilization and perceived implications of AI chatbots in the educational setting.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

Null Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the students' and teachers' perceptions of the pros and cons of using AI chatbots.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized mixed methods, specifically sequential explanatory research, to capture the respondents' insight regarding AI chatbots thoroughly. Creswell (2014) explains that the researcher/s in this approach first conduct quantitative research, analyze the results, and then build on the results to explain them in more detail with qualitative research. It is considered explanatory because the initial quantitative data results are explained further with the qualitative data.

In this study, the researchers initially surveyed to collect quantitative data regarding the pros and cons of AI chatbots, as well as the extent of their use among respondents. In addition, a semi-structured interview was conducted to obtain further insights and explore the phenomenon more comprehensively. Nevertheless, the data was analyzed separately, employing a descriptive comparative method for the quantitative data and a descriptive phenomenological research method for the qualitative data.

In a descriptive-comparative study, researchers describe variables and examine differences in variables in two or more groups that occur naturally in a setting (Grove, 2018). Subsequently, this study describes first the data on the teachers' and students' extents of use and perception of the pros and cons of AI chatbots in education, and investigates the significant differences between the variables tested.

Furthermore, a descriptive phenomenological approach was employed to gain a deeper understanding of this perspective and to provide a more thorough explanation of the phenomenon under investigation.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at the Eastern Samar State University, Maydolong campus. The campus offered six (6) programs, namely Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Criminology (BSCRIM), Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED), Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education (BCAEd), Bachelor of Science in Early Childhood Education (BECED), Bachelor of Science in Elementary Education (BEED), and Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (BTLED).

The University is situated in the southern part of Eastern Samar province, providing services to the specific municipalities of Maydolong, Balangkayan, Llorente, and Hernani to enhance access to education, especially in the more remote areas of these towns.

Figure 2. Map Showing the Locale of the Study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the 59 teaching personnel and the 100 students of the Eastern Samar State University Maydolong campus. The respondents are allocated proportionally and chosen (for the semi-structured interview) according to the researcher's selection process.

Distribution of Respondent Teachers Per Program

Program	Population Size	Percentage
BSHM	15	25.42
BSCRIM	10	16.95
BEED/BECED	12	20.34
BPED	6	10.17
BCAED	6	10.17
BTLED	10	16.95
TOTAL	59	100

Distribution of Respondent Students Per Program

Program	Population Size	Percentage	Sample Size
BSHM	617	43.97	44
BSCRIM	259	18.46	18
BEED	98	6.99	7
BECED	152	10.83	11
BPED	136	9.69	10
BCAED	54	3.85	4
BTLED	87	6.20	6
TOTAL	1,403	100	100

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for the Semi-Structured Interview

For the semi-structured interview, inclusion and exclusion criteria will be established to identify the participants without bias and promote objectivity in the selection process.

For the teacher participants, the inclusion criteria will involve the following:

- The participants must be a regular permanent teacher at ESSU-Maydolong;
- Participants should hold a rank of at least instructor I or their current level with at least 3 to 5 years of teaching experience; and
- Participants must be willing to take part in the study.

The criteria for exclusion in this study are as follows:

- Teachers who are on leave or have a temporary assignment;
- Teachers who do not meet the minimum teaching experience specified by the researchers; and
- Teachers who have previously taken part in similar studies.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria for the students will include the following:

- Must be a bona fide 3rd-year student of ESSU-Maydolong, and hold a good standing (no failing grades, INC, or dropped subjects). On the other hand, those who did not meet the criteria were excluded from taking part in the interview.

Sampling Technique/Procedure

Due to the enormous population of students, the researchers used G-power (version 3.1) to determine the sample size. The result of the power analysis for a two-tailed correlation test indicated that to obtain a statistical power of at least 0.95 with a level of significance (α) of 0.05 and a medium effect size ($\rho = 0.5$), the minimum sample size should be 100. Following that, actual respondents were chosen using random sampling with the use of the lottery method.

To gather data from the faculty, the researchers opted to survey all teaching personnel because there were relatively small numbers of teachers on campus. Thus, a total enumeration was employed to guarantee robust results reflecting teachers' perceptions of the study.

Furthermore, purposive sampling was utilized for the qualitative approach. According to Creswell (2018), purposive sampling is a qualitative research technique that involves selecting participants based on the belief that they will contribute to the study. In this study, the judgment in the selection of the participants was based on the criteria set by the researchers. Five (5) teachers and five (5) students participated in the study. According to Creswell (2018), having between five and thirty participants is suitable for qualitative research; nonetheless, the researcher may include additional participants if saturation has not been achieved. In this study, the information from the participants has already reached saturation, which caused the researcher to conclude that 10 participants can represent the information needed for the qualitative inquiry.

Research Instrument

The researchers modified a research tool from the study "Exploring the Use and Perception of AI-powered Chatbots for Learning: A Survey of CIFS Students at WUIT" (Fakhrudinova, 2024). This research tool was first subjected to a pilot test to assess its accuracy and reliability, with certain parts being omitted or adjusted based on the study's requirements to align with the objectives.

The research tool was organized into 3 sections: The initial section features 10 questions aimed at exploring how frequently respondents utilize the AI chatbot for both learning and instructional purposes, which will be evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale categorized as "Always (5)", "Often (4)", "Sometimes (3)", "Rarely (2)", "Never (1)".

The second part focuses on how respondents perceive the advantages and disadvantages of AI chatbots in the educational sector. Similarly, this part is made up of 10 survey questions. The measurement tool utilized a 5-point Likert scale, which is divided into "Strongly agree (5)," "Agree (4)," "Neutral (3)," "Disagree (2)," and "Strongly Disagree (1)."

The third section was an open-ended question intended for a semi-structured interview. This instrument will be used to form a qualitative inquiry and explain comprehensively the insights of the respondents regarding the perception of the benefits and concerns of AI chatbots in teaching and learning. This guide question was patterned out from the study "Impact of ChatGPT on Higher Education (Dempere et al., 2023)."

Here is the interview guide:

- What benefits and concerns do you perceive in using AI chatbots in learning/teaching?
- How do AI chatbots affect the teaching and learning process in the education context?

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher's initial step was to develop a research tool to gather the needed data for the study. However, before the administration of the instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot test of the questionnaire to a small group of students to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the research tool. Subsequently, various sections of the research questionnaire were adjusted because the results were inconsistent and did not align with the study's objectives.

After the preparation of the research tools, the researchers administered the instrument to the respondents and ensured that assistance was provided for accurate responses. Moreover, after the survey, the researchers set up a semi-structured interview to gather the qualitative data. Before the actual gathering of the data, the researchers first communicated with the participants to ask for consent for the interview and attach the prompts for the interview guide. After the one-on-one interview, the researchers conducted a small group session for the focus group discussion.

Furthermore, the data gathered from the survey was immediately organized, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. Similarly, the data from the interview was cross-validated, organized, and transcribed for a pattern and theme that is aligned with the research questions and objectives.

Data Analysis

The study used a mixed-method approach, which follows a sequential explanatory design, that involves two phases: The initial phase was done through quantitative followed by a qualitative phase to further interpret the findings.

The first phase involved descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the quantitative data, specifically, the percentage was used to summarize the kind of AI chatbots that the respondents were using, and the weighted mean was utilized to describe the perceived benefits and concerns of the respondents in using AI chatbots in education.

Responses are measured using a **5-point Likert scale**, categorizing the extent of use and levels of agreement regarding the pros and cons of AI chatbots. Furthermore, an independent t-test was used to analyze the notable difference in respondents' views of AI chatbots in education (Wilcoxon signed-ranked test was used since it was found out that the data was not normally distributed during the conduct of the assumption test.) The significance level for all tests was set at an alpha of 0.05. The results of this quantitative phase provide an overview of the usage and the pros of cons of AI chatbots in education, which also provide guidelines for the next phase of analysis, which is the qualitative inquiry.

Following that, a qualitative phase was used to understand more deeply the perception of the participants. Specifically, inductive thematic also known as bottom-up or data-driven thematic analysis, was utilized. Inductive thematic analysis is rooted in the principles of grounded theory and explores patterns and themes that emerge directly from the data. According to Rashid (2023), this approach is particularly useful when the research objective is to generate new insights, theories, or understandings from the data without imposing pre-existing theoretical frameworks. Initially, in the qualitative analysis, the researchers first familiarized themselves with the data by reading the transcripts of interviews many times. Second, the researchers highlighted key excerpts, assigned descriptive labels, and generated the initial code, followed by searching for broader themes by grouping the related codes and organizing the themes into a meaningful category that reflected the pattern in the data. Next, the researchers refined the theme and ensured that it aligned with the objectives of the study. Lastly, the researchers finalized the theme and wrote a narrative explaining the scope and significance of each theme.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

AI Chatbots Frequently Used by Students

Table 1 presents the types of AI chatbots commonly utilized by students. The results show that 70 percent of students at Eastern Samar State University in Maydolong utilized ChatGPT as their AI chatbot tool in doing their academic tasks. Additionally, 23 percent of students utilized Meta A.I., while Jenin A.I. represented 7 percent of the overall sample size.

Table 1. AI chatbot Frequently Used by Students

	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Chat GPT	70	70	AI
Meta A.I.	23	23	
Jenin A.I.	7	7	
Total	100	100	

Chatbots Frequently Used by the Teachers

Table 2 displays the AI chatbots commonly utilized by instructors at Eastern Samar State University in Maydolong. The results reveal that the majority (23 or 54.76 percent) of the respondents used Gemini, 6 or 14.28 percent of teachers used ChatGPT, 5 or 11.90 percent opted to use Meta AI, and another 5 or 11.90

percent utilized Jasper Chat, while 2 or 4.76 accounted to used Jenin AI and 1 or 2.38 percent used You chat. This result suggests that the educators had a greater familiarity with various AI chatbot tools.

Table 2. AI Chatbots Frequently Used by the Teachers

Types of AI Chatbots	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Chat GPT	6	14.28
Meta A.I.	5	11.90
Gemini	23	54.76
Jenin A.I.	2	4.76
Jasper Chat	5	11.90
You Chat	1	2.38
Total	42	99.99 or 100

Extent of Use of Students of AI Chatbot

Table 3 presents the extent to which students utilize AI chatbots for their learning. The results indicate that among the ten (10) parameters, parameter 1 got the highest mean score of 4.48 for the statement "I rely on an AI chatbot to generate ideas for my academic work," interpreted as always. This result suggests the significance of AI chatbots in gathering and generating information, as noted by Labadze et al. (2023), who state that AI has the potential to transform the educational landscape in various ways, including providing immediate assistance by answering questions, offering explanations, and supplying additional resources. Additional factors that demonstrated the role of AI in support tasks, such as essay writing, reflection papers, and proofreading and editing, as well as aiding in research writing and boosting creativity in academic output, also received mean scores of 4.41, 4.40, 4.38, and 4.21, respectively. Notably, the prevalence of AI chatbots in research has surged, due to the technology's ability to analyze large volumes of data and uncover patterns of relationships that make it difficult for humans to understand.

Furthermore, the respondents indicated that they often used these AI tools for various purposes, including problem-solving (Mean = 4.19), and completing homework (Mean = 4.18). In addition, AI chatbots were perceived as beneficial in enhancing academic productivity (Mean = 4.12), aiding in the completion of school tasks (Mean = 3.38), and facilitating the planning of academic responsibilities (Mean = 3.26). Overall, the average score of 4.10 suggests that students within this institution actively integrate AI chatbots into their learning processes. Habibi et al. (2024) indicate that the most suitable instructional approach is to not forbid student from using AI, but instead to teach how to effectively use AI to enhance students' learning and creativity, fostering a healthy and collaborative relationship with AI rather than one that is detrimental or overly dependent.

Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. I depend on an AI chatbot to generate ideas for my academic output.	4.48	Always
2. I use AI chatbot as assistance in writing, e.g., essay reflection papers, etc.	4.41	Always
3. I consult AI tools for proofreading or editing my documents.	4.40	Always
4. I use AI chatbots for research-related activities.	4.38	Always

5. I apply AI chatbots to enhance my creativity.	4.21	Always
6. I utilize an AI chatbot as an assistant in solving problems.	4.19	Often
7. I use an AI chatbot for my homework.	4.18	Often
8. I employ an AI chatbot to improve my academic productivity.	4.12	Often
9. I use AI chatbots to complete my school tasks.	3.38	Often
10. I use AI-generated insights in planning my school tasks.	3.26	Often
Grand Mean	4.10	Often

Table 3. Extent of Use of Students of AI Chatbot

Extent of Use of Teachers of AI Chatbot

The results in Table 4 show a moderate use of educators of AI chatbots in their daily activities, with a grand mean of 2.64 interpreted as “Sometimes”. Teachers often use AI chatbots to generate ideas for classroom discussions (Mean = 3.40). Sometimes teachers use AI chatbots to simplify topics and concepts for better understanding (Mean = 3.16), for professional development and research (Mean = 3.03), to create instructional content (Mean = 3.0), and to generate rubrics for students’ assessment (Mean = 2.93). Meanwhile, teachers rarely use AI chatbots for clerical and administrative tasks (Mean = 2.58), to make student quizzes and assignments (Mean = 2.42), to seek assistance from AI chatbots in making course guides and syllabi (Mean = 2.34), to create classroom activities (Mean = 2.26). Notably, the lowest mean was pegged at 1.65, when teachers were asked if they use AI chatbots in giving feedback to students' written output.

These results can be patterned out to Salvador (2024), which emphasize the importance of AI chatbots as a tool for support in lesson planning, however, it is less used for assessment feedback. While educators appreciate the use of AI chatbots in idea creation, most teachers hesitate to use them in evaluative tasks. Similarly, Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) noted the reluctance of teachers to adopt AI for instructional roles, often due to lack of training, which may undermine the teacher's teaching pedagogy. Thus, the integration of AI chatbots in the classroom remains a subject of discussion in the education field.

Table 4. Extent of Use of Teachers of AI Chatbot

Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. I use an AI chatbot to generate ideas for classroom discussion	3.40	Often
2. I use an AI chatbot to simplify topics and concepts for students' understanding.	3.16	Sometimes
2. I use an AI chatbot for professional development and research	3.03	Sometimes
3. I use an AI chatbot to create my instructional content.	3.0	Sometimes
4. I use an AI chatbot to generate rubrics for students’ assessments.	2.93	Sometimes

5. I use an AI chatbot to accomplish clerical or administrative tasks (e.g., reports, letters).	2.58	Rarely
6. I use an AI chatbot to make student quizzes and assignments.	2.42	Rarely
7. I use an AI chatbot to assist in making my syllabus and course guide.	2.34	Rarely
8. I use AI chatbot to create classroom activities	2.26	Rarely
9. I use AI chatbots to give feedback on students' written outputs.	1.65	Never
Grand Mean	2.67	Sometimes

Students Perceived Pros of AI Chatbot

The results of table 5 show a favorable perception of the students regarding the use of AI chatbots in education with a grand mean of 4.05, interpreted as “Agree”. Notably, the students strongly agree with the statement “AI chatbot can help save time” with the highest mean score of 4.45, followed by the statement “Illuminate ideas in writing to improve efficacy” (Mean = 4.41), “Provide information in diverse fields” (Mean = 4.38), which indicates that users acknowledge the significance of AI chatbots in enhancing academic requirements. Students also recognized AI chatbots' potential to generate and assist their learning, as reflected in their strong agreement on the statements involving creative idea formulation (Mean = 4.36), translation of learning materials (Mean = 4.32), easy understanding of concepts and theories (Mean 4.29). Kesneci et al. (2023) argue that generative AI tools such as ChatGPT are valuable for enhancing learning, fostering creativity, and facilitating knowledge acquisition by providing rapid access and relevant information.

Table 5. Students' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbot

Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. AI chatbots can help save time	4.45	Strongly Agree
2. AI chatbots can illuminate ideas in writing, thus improving efficiency and productivity	4.41	Strongly Agree
3. AI chatbots can provide information in diverse fields	4.38	Strongly Agree
4. AI chatbots can help formulate a creative idea	4.36	Strongly Agree
5. AI chatbots can help to translate learning materials into different languages, making them easy to access	4.32	Strongly Agree
6. AI chatbots can help better understand concepts and theories	4.29	Strongly Agree
7. AI chatbots can help in problem-solving tasks	4.20	Agree
8. AI chatbots can help enhance learning by offering a personalized and adaptive learning experience	3.42	Agree
9. AI chatbots can provide personalized tutoring and feedback based on the learning needs and progress	3.40	Agree

10. AI chatbots can help improve critical thinking ability	3.31	Neutral
Grand Mean	4.05	Agree

Furthermore, students agree with the statements that “AI chatbots can help in problem-solving tasks” (Mean = 4.20), “Enhance learning by offering a personalized and adaptive learning experience” (Mean = 3.42), and “Tutoring and feedback” (Mean = 3.40), and neutral when it comes to its ability to enhance critical thinking skill (Mean = 3.31). These results indicate that while users recognized the AI chatbot information support, students were cautious of its deeper ability such as improving their critical thinking. **Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019)**, emphasize that AI may hold promise for personalized learning but experts have difficulty trusting this technology most especially in its provision to give feedback and critical thinking development. Holstein (2019), noted the positive side of AI systems by enhancing the classroom experience. However, the author stressed that users need to be cautious about overreliance on said technology, since it may limit deep learning and critical reflection.

Students' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbot

The results in Table 5.1 reveal students' concerns about the use of AI chatbots in education, with a grand mean of 3.85 showing the respondents' overall agreement with the posed concerns of this technology. The highest-rated statements, with a mean of 4.52, show that respondents strongly agreed that too much dependence on AI chatbots could lead to addiction to this technology. Akbar et al. (2023) suggest that students are becoming increasingly reliant on AI chatbots for academic tasks, which hinders students' critical thinking, reflection, and self-learning. Similarly, a high mean score was computed with the statements “AI chatbots adversely affect critical thinking” (Mean = 4.48), and “Creative writing skills” (Mean 4.39), in which students recognized concerns that too much use of this technology might diminish their deep learning and originality of ideas. Zou & Zou (2023), emphasize that when students use AI chatbots daily, they may bypass their cognitive process which is vital in critical thinking and problem-solving.

Additionally, students agree that they have concerns that AI chatbots may lead to plagiarism and other academic fraud (Mean = 4.20), provide unreliable data (Mean 4.19), and inaccurate references (Mean = 3.68). These results indicate the student's concerns about the reliability of information generated by AI chatbots.

Meanwhile, statements regarding ethical concerns and the broader impact of AI chatbots on the purpose of education received neutral responses. This suggests while there are a lot of questions about unethical concerns in the use of this technology, respondents are still divided on its use in an overall education context. Akbar et al. (2024) suggest that even though there is a pressing need for clear ethical guidelines, experts may formulate educational policies to navigate the AI chatbot integration in education. Overall, while AI chatbots possess benefits, the findings underscore the significance of using this technology with a certain balance.

Table 5.1. Students' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbot

	Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1.	Too much dependence on AI chatbots could lead to addiction to this technology.	4.52	Strongly Agree
2.	AI chatbots adversely affect critical thinking and problem-solving capabilities.	4.48	Strongly Agree
3.	AI chatbots adversely affect creative writing skills.	4.39	Strongly Agree

4. AI chatbots violate academic integrity due to issues of plagiarism and other academic fraud.	4.20	Agree
5. AI chatbots provide unreliable data, threatening information credibility.	4.19	Agree
6. AI chatbots can produce inaccurate or false factual references	3.68	Agree
7. It is unethical to depend on AI chatbots to write academic tasks.	3.31	Neutral
8. I am concerned about the ethical issue of using AI chatbots.	3.29	Neutral
9. I am concerned that using AI chatbots may undermine academic assessment fairness and accuracy.	3.23	Neutral
10. I am concerned that AI chatbot dependency can destroy the purpose of education.	3.21	Neutral

Grand Mean	3.85	Agree
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Teachers Perceived Pros of AI Chatbot

Results in Table 6 reflect the educators perceived benefits of AI chatbots in education. A grand mean of 4.01 suggests an agreement with the positive effect of using this technology in their daily teaching and activities. Teachers strongly agree that AI chatbots can save time (Mean = 4.5), assist in translating learning materials into different languages (Mean = 4.4), and provide information across diverse fields (Mean = 4.29). These findings suggest the teacher's practicality of the teachers in using this technology in managing a variety of tasks in a time-constraint setting, as well as the ability of this technology to generate responses. According to Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019), AI technologies are increasingly used for automating ideas, thus allowing educators to save more time in finding information and other tasks assigned to them.

There is also general agreement among the teachers that AI chatbots illuminate ideas (Mean = 4.15), enhance personalized learning (Mean = 4.03), and support problem-solving (Mean=4.02). These findings were aligned with the study of Holmes (2019), who noted that AI systems can scaffold learning and provide real-time support and tailored responses based on the user's needs.

Teachers also believe that AI can assist in understanding concepts and theories (Mean= 4.00), and deliver personalized feedback (Mean=3.96), which aligns with the study of Chen et al (2020), who averred that AI chatbots can significantly improve learners through the technology ability to act as a virtual tutor that complements with the traditional teaching.

Table 6 Teachers' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbot

Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. AI chatbots can help save time	4.5	Strongly Agree
2. AI chatbots can help to translate learning materials into different languages, making them easy to access	4.4	Strongly Agree
3. AI chatbots can provide information in diverse fields	4.29	Strongly Agree

4. AI chatbots can illuminate ideas in writing, thus improving efficiency and productivity	4.15	Agree
5. AI chatbots can help enhance learning by offering a personalized and adaptive learning experience	4.03	Agree
6. AI chatbots can help in problem-solving tasks	4.02	Agree
7. AI chatbots can help better understand concepts and theories	4.0	Agree
8. AI chatbots can provide personalized tutoring and feedback based on the learning needs and progress	3.96	Agree
9. AI chatbots can help formulate a creative idea	3.52	Agree
10. AI chatbots can help improve critical thinking ability	3.32	Neutral
Grand Mean	4.01	Agree

Interestingly, while teachers agree that AI can help formulate ideas (Mean = 3.52), they are neutral regarding the role of AI chatbots in enhancing critical thinking skills (Mean = 3.32). Luckin et al. (2017) note that critical thinking is often developed through rich discussion, inquiry, and reflection, which is not fostered in AI systems.

In general, teachers acknowledge the benefits of AI chatbots such as efficiency, accessibility, and individualized support. However, they also recognized the limitations of this technology most especially in cultivating higher thinking-order skills.

Teachers Perceived Cons of AI Chatbot

The results show the concern of teachers regarding the use of AI chatbots in education. A grand mean of 4.01 suggests an agreement pointing toward the negative impact of this technology. The highest concern of the teachers is that AI chatbots might reduce fairness and accuracy in students' assessments (Mean = 3.96). This concern is highlighted by Awad and Moosa (2024), stating that AI use must be managed to protect fairness and reliability in student assessment.

Another concern of the teachers is students becoming too dependent on AI, which could lead to addiction to much use of this technology (Mean = 3.94). Due to the capabilities of AI to generate information, students may lose motivation to think for themselves, as observed by Aleedy et al. (2022) stating that too much dependency on this technology can weaken students' ability to think independently.

Teachers also agreed that AI chatbots make the students less critical (Mean = 3.93) and creative thinkers (3.90). This result is valid as AI chatbots can offer ready-made answers, which hinders students' ability to think and solve problems. Sidorkin (2024) noted that while AI can support learning, it should never replace human effort and imagination. Teachers also agreed that AI chatbots may slowly take away the purpose of education (Mean = 3.75). Moreover, teachers also agreed that it is unethical to use AI chatbots for academic tasks (Mean = 3.74).

Lastly, teachers also expressed concerns over unreliable information (Mean = 3.59) plagiarism, other forms of academic fraud (Mean = 3.53), and false references, (Mean = 3.43) provided by AI chatbots.

Table 6. 1 Teachers' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbot

Statements	Mean	Adjectival Interpretation
1. I am concerned that using AI chatbots may undermine academic assessment fairness and accuracy.	3.96	Agree
2. Too much dependence on AI chatbots could lead to addiction to this technology.	3.94	Agree
3. AI chatbots adversely affect critical thinking and problem-solving capabilities.	3.93	Agree
4. AI chatbots adversely affect creative writing skills.	3.90	Agree
5. I am concerned that AI chatbot dependency can destroy the purpose of education.	3.75	Agree
6. I am concerned about the ethical issue of using AI chatbots.	3.75	Agree
7. It is unethical to depend on AI chatbots to write academic tasks.	3.74	Agree
8. AI chatbots provide unreliable data threatening information credibility.	3.59	Agree
9. AI chatbots violate academic integrity due to issues of plagiarism and other academic fraud.	3.53	Agree
10. AI chatbots can produce inaccurate or false factual references	3.43	Agree
Grand Mean	4.01	Agree

Comparative Analysis
Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk) for Teachers and Students' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbots

Before deciding which statistical test to use, the data were first checked for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The results showed that the responses for both teachers ($W = 0.910$, $p = 0.004$) and students ($W = 0.905$, $p = 0.003$) were not normally distributed. Given this, a non-parametric test was more appropriate. The **Wilcoxon signed-rank test** was chosen since it works well with non-normal data and is suitable, especially when using Likert scale responses. This allowed for a more accurate and reliable analysis of how respondents perceived the pros of AI chatbots.

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk) of Teachers and Students Perceived Pros of AI Chatbot

	W	P
Teachers Perceived Pros	0.910	0.004
Students Perceived Pros	0.905	0.003

Note: Significant results suggest a deviation from normality

Comparative Analysis of Teachers' and Students' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbots

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed that there is a strong and significant difference between how teachers and students perceive the pros of AI chatbots ($p < 0.001$). The test statistic of 820.000 and the Rank-Biserial Correlation of 1.000 suggest that the difference in perceptions is very large, meaning that teachers and students have very different views on the pros of AI chatbots. The small standard error (0.179) also indicates that this difference is measured with high accuracy. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, stating that there is no significant difference between the respondents' perceived pros of AI chatbots.

Table. 7 Wilcoxon signed-rank test

	v	p	Rank-Biserial Correlation	SE Rank-Biserial Correlation
Teachers and Students' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbots	820.000	< .001	1.000	0.179

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk) for Teachers and Students' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbots

In this condition, where the teachers' perceived concerns ($W = 0.947, p = 0.60$) showed that the data is approximately normal, and students' perceived concerns ($W = 0.913, p = 0.00$), suggest that it is not normally distributed. The researchers still used the Wilcoxon signed-rank test because at least one group violated normality.

Test of Normality (Shapiro-Wilk) of Teachers and Students' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbots

	W	P
Teachers Perceived Cons	0.947	0.060
Students Perceived Cons	0.913	0.050

Note: Significant results suggest a deviation from normality

Comparative Analysis of Teachers' and Students' Perceived Pros of AI Chatbots

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test showed a clear and significant difference between how teachers and students view the cons or drawbacks of AI chatbots. The test result was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), which means this difference is unlikely to be due to chance.

The rank-biserial correlation was 1.000, indicating a very strong effect size. This means that teachers and students had completely different views on the negative aspects of AI chatbots. The standard error (0.179) was small, which tells us the result is quite precise and reliable. Therefore, the researchers rejected the null hypothesis.

Table 7.1. Wilcoxon signed-rank test

	v	p	Rank-Biserial Correlation	SE Rank- Biserial Correlation
Teachers and Students' Perceived Cons of AI Chatbots	820.000	< .001	1.000	0.179

THEMATIC ANALYSIS

THEME

AI Chatbots as Helpful Companions with Hidden Costs in Learning

AI Chatbots have become valuable companions for both students and teachers in the classroom. This technology is increasingly needed for streamlining workloads, quick access to information, etc. For many students, the AI chatbot is sometimes useful for clarifying and creating ideas. According to Lin et al. (2024), this shift is described as “Learning Augmentation,” where AI assists learners by filling in gaps, explaining content, or modeling how to solve problems.

However, while the support can be empowering, it also comes with trade-offs. As users become more reliant on AI for fast answers, some begin to skip thinking. Students sometimes do not even look at the learning materials, instead, they become content with what the chatbots can suggest. Wu and Yu. (2024), caution that this may weaken students’ problem-solving abilities over time, especially when learners begin outsourcing thinking to technology.

Creativity can also take a hit. As users become too dependent on AI chatbots. One might end up letting AI generate ideas. Students may forget the unique way they express themselves. As Craft (2010) emphasizes, creativity thrives in uncertainty and struggle, and when students no longer push themselves through that process, they may miss out on some of the most meaningful parts of learning. AI chatbots are like scaffolds—useful for support, but not meant to be leaned on forever. They can help students grow, but only if used in balance.

There’s also a deeper question of trust. When teachers read students’ output, it can be hard to tell if a student wrote it. The line between assistance and dishonesty is becoming increasingly blurred in this digital age. This uncertainty creates tension in classrooms, where academic integrity used to be more straightforward.

SUBTHEMES

AI Chatbots Enhance Task Efficiency and Access to Knowledge.

Nowadays, teachers and students alike are turning to AI chatbots as support in managing their workload. From the results of the study, both students and teachers acknowledged the benefits of AI chatbots in education. The most notable benefit is the ability of this technology to save time. Both students (mean = 4.45) and teachers (mean = 4.50) strongly agreed on this parameter. As SP1 shared “*I can finish my academic task much faster than expected with the help of AI chatbot like ChatGPT to clarify what I don’t understand and for the fast information it generates*” Teachers also echoed this ability of AI chatbots “*I can find my work much easier and faster when I used this technology. For example, I manage my lessons with the ability of AI Chatbots to simplify topics and generate information, which makes my instruction and clerical tasks easier (TP1&2).*” These results highlight the significant role of AI chatbots in simplifying tasks and allowing more time for actual learning and teaching (Zawacki-Richter et al. 2019).

Similarly, both teachers and students also agreed that using an AI chatbot expands their knowledge due to users can access a wide range of information. One of the students explained, *“If I don’t understand something in class, I can just ask the chatbot, and it gives me so many different explanations and examples”* (SP3). Teachers also recognized this benefit as they said, *“It’s like having a personal research assistant. I can get information on any topic to supplement my lessons”* (TP 4 & 5). Holmes et al. (2019), argued that AI chatbots can alleviate the burden by streamlining information retrieval and supporting more efficient learning.

AI chatbots allow the end user to access wide information quickly. While this technology is undeniably helpful, it is significant to be mindful of the need for students to develop critical thinking skills.

The integration of this kind of technology is not smooth sailing. The study also revealed some concerns, especially, about its impact on users' critical thinking and problem-solving ability. While teachers and students acknowledge the benefits of saving time and widening their knowledge. Both students (Mean = 3.31) and teachers (Mean = 3.32) are concerned that this technology helps improve their critical thinking skills. During the FGD, teachers shared *“Students are getting quick answers, but they’re not really thinking critically about the material. It’s like they’re taking shortcuts rather than grappling with the concepts themselves.”* Students also shared, *“Sometimes I just copied information or ideas fed by the AI chatbots, especially when I want to catch the deadline for an assignment, etc.”* (SP4).

Another concern that emerged is the sudden loss of students’ creativity. Both students and teachers were worried that using AI might stifle their ability to create the student's own ideas. One student said, *“I sometimes feel like I’m not being as creative because I rely on the chatbot for ideas.”* Teachers seemed to share the same concern, stating *“I’ve seen students becoming too independent on AI for everything, it seems that even simple essays, reflection papers, brainstorming, etc are too difficult for them to think on their own and outside the box”* (TP 3&5, FGD). Luckin et al. (2022) noted that while an AI chatbot can be a helpful tool, it’s no substitute for the kind of deep thinking that comes from engaging with challenging material.

Excessive Dependence on AI Chatbots Hinders Critical Thinking.

AI chatbots have been increasingly acknowledged as a powerful tool for personalized learning. The quantitative inquiry showed moderate agreement between both teachers and students. One of the students stated, *“When I don’t understand something in class, I can ask the chatbot, and it provides me with explanations”* (SP3). Teachers shared similar thoughts; however, they emphasized the concern of the students being over-reliant on such technology. As noted by a teacher, *“While chatbots are helpful to my students when they need quick responses or when they ask chatbots to generate some answers, it will not replace humans in guiding them through a complex problem and encouraging them to think critically”* (TP 1&5). This limitation is highlighted in some literature, where experts such as Holmes (2019) explained that while AI chatbots can personalize learning to some degree, they fall short in replicating deeper thinking. AI may help students learn at their own pace, but when it comes to fostering critical thinking, AI has much room to grow.

AI chatbots are seen by the students as scaffolding tools – ready to guide them, simplify complex problems, and provide ready-made answers. As stated by students during the FGD *“Sometimes, when I’m overwhelmed, it’s just easier to let the chatbot explain everything—or even write something for me if I’m stuck”* (SP4). One teacher observed, *“I notice students become too dependent. They stop struggling with concepts on their own and just let the chatbot think”* (TP2). AI can support students, but when that support turns into dependence, it will be a risk that undermines the purpose of education. As Vardi and Choudhary (2024) wisely put it, *“AI should be a lens that sharpens human insight, not a veil that replaces it.”*

AI Chatbot Use Raises Concerns About Plagiarism and Academic Honesty.

Teachers raised concerns regarding how AI chatbots could undermine academic integrity. Notwithstanding the technology's potential to improve the education landscape, the said technology could also increase the risk of academic dishonesty. As one of the teachers commented, *“I am afraid that time*

will come when students only answer their assignment without even understanding the concept (TP 1&2 FGD). Educause recently reported that the concern is that chatbots may produce well-written material that is impossible to detect, making it challenging to ensure the integrity of academic work.

Teachers are also concerned about plagiarism and cheating, as stated by one participant: “*The students simply copied the information generated by Chatbots without knowing the brain behind the idea (TP 5)*” and “*due to the ability of Chatbots to directly answer queries, I am afraid that the cheating is much easier (TP 3).*” **Susnjak (2022)** warned that the availability of sophisticated AI-generated responses may erode academic integrity and make traditional forms of plagiarism detection less effective. Both students and teachers agreed on their concerns about AI chatbot's integrity in academic work. While AI chatbots can help students with their academic output such as assignments, etc. there is also a risk of plagiarism or academic dishonesty. As is reflected in the statement “AI chatbots violate academic integrity due to plagiarism” (Mean = 3.53) on the students. Teachers shared. “*it's hard to tell whether it is students' work or it is generated by the AI, and if the students verify the references for the information. Sometimes it creates trust issues in the classroom.*” (TP 1& 2). Akbar et al. (2025), noted that AI tools, while useful, can sometimes be misused for academic shortcuts, leading to a loss of authenticity in students' work.

Such findings worry a lot on the part of the teacher since giving assessments is one of their priorities to measure the learning of the students.

Unverified AI-Generated Content Challenges Information Accuracy.

Teachers expressed concerns about AI chatbot information reliability as there is a wide range of sources and ideas provided, which can also lead to students' confusion. As stated by one of the teachers, “It's frustrating as students rely so much on this platform without double-checking if the information, they obtain is truly trustworthy (TP 2).”

Students and teachers alike complain about the misleading information provided by chatbots like ChatGPT, as they cannot perform tasks that are specifically related to a particular concept. “*Although chatbots provide factual information, some students still can't verify if that answer is related to what they are looking for (TP 3,4,&5 FGD).*”

Students commented, “*It is difficult to verify information since there are no cited authors or references to the information produced by chatbots (SP 1).*”

As such, the discovery of chatbots' occasional incorrect information and lack of sources for the data generated can mislead students and lead them to receive inaccurate knowledge (Bender et al. 2024).

Summary

AI Chatbots have become valuable companions for both students and teachers in the classroom. As the debate about this tool's integration into education grows, it is imperative to understand the perception of students and teachers regarding this technology. Accordingly, this study delves deeper into understanding this perception using a mixed-method approach, specifically, a sequential exploratory where the researchers conducted first a quantitative followed by a qualitative phase. The researchers utilized random sampling through the use of G-power to determine the sample size (100) for the students, total enumeration for teachers (42), and purposive sampling for the qualitative approach with a total of 5 participants for students and 5 for the teachers.

The first phase of the study was quantitative in which the results showed that most of the respondents used ChatGPT as a tool for their daily activities, however, students often used AI chatbots while teachers sometimes used the said technology. Results also revealed that students agreed with the pros of AI chatbots (Grand Mean = 4.05) and cons (3.85). Additionally, the teachers also agreed on the pros (4.01), and Cons (4.01) of the AI chatbots. Notably, the students are more hesitant to recognize the negative implications of AI chatbots, rather than how it is perceived negatively by the teachers. Lastly, the results

indicated a significant difference in how respondents perceived AI chatbot implementation in education. This could be attributed to their respective roles and experiences in the learning environment—teachers could think more in terms of the implications and difficulty for instruction, evaluation, and classroom management, while students would see AI chatbots differently as accessible resources providing instant assistance, support, and interaction with learning content.

The second phase of the study was qualitative, in which it formulated the theme “AI Chatbots as Helpful Companions with Hidden Costs in Learning” and the following subthemes: (1) AI Chatbots Enhance Task Efficiency and Access to Knowledge, (2) Excessive Dependence on AI Chatbots Hinders Critical Thinking, (3) AI Chatbot Use Raises Concerns About Plagiarism and Academic Honesty, (4) Unverified AI-Generated Content Challenges Information Accuracy.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. 70 percent of students at Eastern Samar State University in Maydolong utilized ChatGPT as their AI chatbot tool in doing their academic tasks. Additionally, 23 percent of students utilized Meta A.I., while Jenin A.I. represented 7 percent of the overall sample size.
2. The majority (23 or 54.76 percent) of the teachers used Gemini, 6 or 14.28 percent of teachers used ChatGPT, 5 or 11.90 percent opted to use Meta AI, and another 5 or 11.90 percent utilized Jasper Chat, while 2 or 4.76 accounted to used Jenin AI and 1 or 2.38 percent used You chat. This result suggests that the educators had a greater familiarity with various AI chatbot tools.
3. The students’ average score of 4.10 indicates that learners are not just using AI Chatbots frequently, but rather, integrating it into their learning routine. Results show a growing dependence of students on this technology within the education landscape, especially with students becoming fond of its capability to generate answers that limit creativity, problem-solving, and critical thinking.
4. The findings reveal that while educators are slowly integrating AI chatbots into teaching, However, the overall extent of use appears to be low. With a grand mean of 2.64, teachers appear to moderately engage with AI Chatbots, educators use them only sometimes. Engagement with the AI appears to be strongest in brainstorming and simplifying content, but low in assessment construction, clerical and administrative work, and in providing feedback to learners.
5. The findings suggest students have a positive perception of AI chatbots with a grand mean of 4.05 “Agree” which shows that students recognize the value AI holds in helping them accomplish tasks such as saving time, generating ideas, and explaining complex concepts. Students affirmed AI’s role in enhancing productivity, and creativity and providing information across subjects. This is also supported by the qualitative findings where student participants explained the significance of AI chatbots as a companion for their everyday learning and emphasized the technology’s ability to provide ready-made answers which saved them more of their time. However, students have expressed concerns about too much dependence on AI chatbots with a grand mean of 3.85 especially around potential addiction, critical and creative thinking skills, and writing skills. Concerns about plagiarism along with unreliable data and incorrect references produced by AI are also a concern. Participants did express agreement on ethical issues as well as AI and education which suggests some indifference. In general, students emphasize the advantages of AI and its use, however, they highlighted the need to moderate its use and ensure information accuracy to protect academic integrity.
6. Teachers agreed on the practical advantages of AI chatbots in teaching, particularly in saving time, translating content, and retrieving wide information. With a grand mean of 4.01, they tend to concur that AI facilitates teaching tasks, improves tailored learning, and assists in conceptual explanation, so it is a valuable tool within the current fast-paced classroom setting. However, educators showed reservations regarding applying AI chatbots to education, with a grand mean of 4.01 supporting overall agreement with their possible negative effects. Their biggest concerns relate to the fairness

of evaluation, student overreliance, and the decline of critical and creative thought. Although recognizing the strengths of AI, instructors emphasize preserving educational integrity, human judgment, and the real objective of learning.

7. Results indicated a significant difference in how respondents perceived AI chatbot implementation in education. This could be attributed to their respective roles and experiences in the learning environment—teachers could think more in terms of the implications and difficulty for instruction, evaluation, and classroom management, while students would see AI chatbots differently as accessible resources providing instant assistance, support, and interaction with learning content.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were considered:

1. To narrow the gap of familiarity with AI tools and to enhance more efficient collaboration, it is recommended to carry out a capacity-building program regularly. The workshop must involve familiarization with the diverse AI platforms, highlighting AI capabilities, ethical issues, and applications in learning. This approach could result in the user's digital literacy.
2. Eastern Samar State University in Maydolong should implement programs that promote responsible AI use among students by integrating digital literacy and ethical AI use into the curriculum. The school should also conduct seminars and workshops to raise awareness about the benefits and limitations of AI tools, encourage critical thinking and originality in academic tasks, and establish clear policies on the acceptable use of AI to protect academic integrity and support meaningful learning.
3. It is recommended to offer opportunities that support the responsible use of AI in the classroom. In addition, educators must define and establish the appropriate boundaries when it comes to AI use so that it enhances, not out-scales, the development of the vital cognitive skills of our learners.
4. Eastern Samar State University should acknowledge the differences in perception between the teachers' implementation in contrast with their students' use of an AI chatbot. The data from this study can be used as a baseline for researchers to conduct further studies on how AI chatbots can be optimized in the teaching and learning environment (more on the technical aspect) or conduct studies that will delve deeper into understanding how AI engagement affects students' academic performance.

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